

DiSSCo-ITINERIS community: definition and activities

DiSSCo-ITINERIS community is part of the Next Generation EU (PNRR) project ITINERIS (“Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System”, project no. IR0000032 - itineris.cnr.it), aimed at coordinating and integrating the Italian nodes of 22 European Research Infrastructures (RI).

ITINERIS will build the Italian Hub of Research Infrastructures in the environmental scientific domain for the observation and study of environmental processes in the atmosphere, marine domain, terrestrial biosphere, and geosphere, providing access to data and services and supporting the Country to address current and expected environmental challenges.

The DiSSCo-ITINERIS community comprises eleven institutions in Italy:

- The Florence University Museum System, University of Florence (UNIFI-SMA) (<https://www.sma.unifi.it/>) - contact persons: Gianna Innocenti, gianna.innocenti@unifi.it; Lorenzo Cecchi – l.cecchi@unifi.it
- The Institute of Biosciences and BioResources, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IBBR) (<https://ibbr.cnr.it>) - contact person: Gabriele Bucci, gabriele.bucci@cnr.it
- The Institute of Marine Sciences, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISMAR) (<https://www.ismar.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Simona Armeli Minicante, simona.armeliminicante@cnr.it; Laura Giordano, laura.giordano@cnr.it; Irene Guarneri, irene.guarneri@cnr.it
- The Water Research Institute, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IRSA) (<https://www.irsa.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Diego Fontaneto, diego.fontaneto@cnr.it; Andrea Buffagni, andrea.buffagni@cnr.it, Antonella Petrocelli, antonella.petrocelli@cnr.it
- The Institute of Biology and Agricultural Biotechnology, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IBBA) (<https://ibba.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Laura Morello, lauraemmamaria.morello@cnr.it
- The Institute of BioEconomy, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IBE) (<https://www.ibe.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Sabrina Palanti, sabrina.palanti@cnr.it
- The Institute of Sustainable Protection of Plants, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IPSP) (<http://www.ipsp.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Roberto Danti, roberto.danti@cnr.it
- The Institute of Food Sciences, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISA) (<https://www.isa.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Antonio d’Acierno, antino.dacierno@cnr.it
- The Institute of Mediterranean Agricultural and Forest Systems (CNR-ISAFOM) (<https://www.isafom.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Giuseppe Diego Puglia, giuseppediego.puglia@cnr.it
- The Institute of Biological Systems, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISB) (<http://www.isb.cnr.it/>) - Francesca Mariani, francesca.mariani@cnr.it
- The Institute of Food Production Sciences, National Council of Research (CNR-ISPA) (<https://www.ispa.cnr.it/>) - Giancarlo Perrone, giancarlo.perrone@cnr.it

- The Institute for the Animal Production System in the Mediterranean Environment, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISPAAM) (<https://www.ispaam.cnr.it/>) - contact persons: Chiara D'Ambrosio, chiara.dambrosio@cnr.it

The operating units (OU) involved in the WP6 “Terrestrial Biosphere” of the ITINERIS project and responsible for the following project activities:

- **Activity 6.4:** “Italian natural history collections (NHCs)” (OU UNIFI-SMA) (contact persons: Gianna Innocenti, gianna.innocenti@unifi.it; Lorenzo Cecchi – l.cecchi@unifi.it);
- **Activity 6.5:** “Mining and mapping the functional biodiversity in *in vivo* and *ex-situ* research collections” - (OU CNR-IBBR-BA) (contact persons: Raffaella Balestrini, raffaellamaria.balestrini@cnr.it, Gabriele Bucci, gabriele.bucci@cnr.it);
- **Activity 6.6:** “National network of the aquatic science collections” (OU CNR-ISMAR-VE) (contact persons: Simona Armeli Minicante, simona.armeliminicante@cnr.it; Laura Giordano, laura.giordano@cnr.it; Irene Guarneri, irene.guarneri@cnr.it).

In the frame of this project, the DiSSCo-ITINERIS website (<https://www.dissco-itineris.it/>) hosts the results of the three activities taking part in the construction of one of the Italian nodes of the European Research Infrastructure DiSSCo-ERIC (Distributed System of Scientific Collections - www.dissco.eu).

S. Armeli Minicante, G. Bucci, A. Buffagni, L. Cecchi, D. Fontaneto, L. Giordano, V. Grande, I. Guarneri, G. Innocenti, L. Spada and DiSSCo-ITINERIS members

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